

Soft Federated Learning and Its Application in Construction of Radiobiological Effect Prediction Model in Multi-Center Scenario

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A new soft federated learning algorithm is proposed and applied to construct a more accurate radiobiological effect prediction model in a multi-center scenario. Theoretical analysis shows that the soft federated learning algorithm can construct a federated model with better prediction performance by only sharing a small amount of data between different centers. Experimental results show that the prediction performance of the federated model generated by the soft federated learning algorithm in the construction of the radiobiological effect prediction model in a multi-center scenario is better than that of the prediction model generated by other commonly used methods. Theoretical analysis and experimental results show that the soft federated learning algorithm has the potential to be used to alleviate the anti-globalization trend of current artificial intelligence technology in some specific fields.

Key words: Federated learning; Radiobiological effect prediction model; Artificial intelligence; FLASH

Purpose

High-quality data plays a decisive role in building advanced artificial intelligence prediction models ¹⁻³. However, different countries tend to restrict the sharing of certain specific data for different reasons, which makes the current development of artificial intelligence technology in some specific fields show a trend of anti-globalization. For example, in the field of radiotherapy, FLASH ⁴⁻⁶ is a novel therapeutic radiation modality that holds remarkable potential for mitigating radiation therapy's adverse side effects. The related radiobiological effect experimental data can be used to build the FLASH radiobiological effect prediction model, which is crucial for promoting the implementation of FLASH radiation physics equipment in the medical field. The establishment of a radiobiological effect prediction model generally refers to the establishment of a mapping relationship between radiological quantities related to radiation physics rays and the biological response of cells or tissues to them based on radiobiological experimental data (such as radiation dose-cell survival fraction, etc.), providing a tool basis for better leveraging the practical application value of radiation physics rays in the medical field ⁷. However, in order to protect advanced scientific research results, some countries are likely to attach importance to the security management of related data and restrict the sharing of FLASH radiobiological effect experimental data, thereby hindering the development of FLASH radiobiological effect prediction models based on artificial intelligence algorithms in multi-center scenarios. Federated learning ⁸ is a feasible artificial intelligence algorithm strategy to alleviate this situation. It first builds

a prediction model based on the localization of independent data from each center, and then centrally manages the prediction models from each center to form a federated model for actual prediction, so that each center only needs to share its prediction model and avoid sharing its data. However, since the data of each center is not visible to the localized prediction model construction process of other centers, when the localized models of different centers predict data from other centers, large errors will inevitably occur, which will affect the prediction accuracy of the final federated model. This paper aims to propose a new artificial intelligence algorithm and apply it to build more accurate radiobiological effect prediction models in a multi-center scenario.

Methods

A new soft federated learning algorithm is proposed. The theoretical premise of the algorithm is that there are some centers willing to share their data; this is different from the theoretical premise of the usual federated learning algorithm⁸, that is, there are no centers willing to share their data. Due to the different theoretical assumptions proposed by the algorithm, soft federated learning is a new artificial intelligence algorithm strategy compared with the usual federated learning. Based on the feasible and realistic theoretical premise that "there are some centers willing to share their data", in theory, the soft federated learning algorithm only needs different centers to share a small part of the data to build a federated model with better prediction performance. The reason is that a collection of a small amount of data shared by different centers forms a public dataset visible to all centers. Since this dataset contains data from different centers, it has good diversity and can be used to improve the generalization ability of the prediction models constructed locally by different centers on the test data of other centers.

Based on a set of experimental data of radiobiological effects (radiation dose-cell survival fraction)⁹, this paper simulates and implements the basic process of applying soft federated learning algorithm to build a more accurate prediction model. The specific steps are as follows:

- 1) By adding noise of different distributions to the obtained dose-survival fraction experimental data D , repeat 10 times to simulate data $\{D_1, \dots, D_{10}\}$ from 10 different centers.
- 2) The data of each of the 10 centers $\{D_1, \dots, D_{10}\}$ are divided respectively. For center i : 80% of the data is randomly selected as training data $Train_i$, 10% of the data is used as shared data $Share_i$, and the remaining 10% of the data is used as test data $Test_i$ from the center; $D_i = \{Train_i, Share_i, Test_i\}$. In particular, the union of shared data from different centers $\{Share_1, \dots, Share_{10}\}$ constitutes publicly accessible public data, and the union of test data from different centers $\{Test_1, \dots, Test_{10}\}$ constitutes test data in real application scenarios.
- 3) Based on the training data $Train_1, \dots, Train_{10}$, the localized models of 10 centers $Model_1, \dots, Model_{10}$ are fitted based on the LQ (Linear Quadratic) model^{10,11}.
- 4) The 10 fitted models $Model_1, \dots, Model_{10}$ are used to predict the data $\{Share_1, \dots, Share_{10}\}$, and the weights of the 10 fitted models are estimated based on the prediction results. More specifically, different strategies can be used to estimate the model weights, such as 1) mean weight, 2) error-ratio weight or 3) fitted weight.
- 5) Based on the estimated weights, the 10 fitted models are weighted and centrally managed to construct the final federated prediction model. In particular, the federated prediction model composed of different estimated weights can represent the output model of different federated learning algorithms; when the mean weight is used, the constructed federated prediction model is

the output model of the usual federated learning algorithm; when the error-ratio weight or fitted weight is used, the constructed federated prediction model is the output model of the soft federated learning algorithm proposed in this paper.

- 6) The prediction models produced by different federated learning algorithms are compared and tested on the $\{Test_1, \dots, Test_{10}\}$ dataset, and the advantages and disadvantages of different algorithms are reflected by evaluating the generalization ability of different models.

Figure 1. Basic process of the soft federated learning.

In addition to implementing the usual federated learning algorithm (using average weights to form a federated model) and the soft federated learning algorithm (using error proportion weights and fitting weights to form a federated model), this paper also implements a method for establishing a prediction model based on the data of each single center $\{Train_i, Share_i\}$ and a method for establishing a prediction model based on multi-center data union $\{\{Train_1, \dots, Train_{10}\}, \{Share_1, \dots, Share_{10}\}\}$. By comparing the errors of the prediction models constructed by these different methods on the multi-center test set $\{Test_1, \dots, Test_{10}\}$, the application potential of the soft federated learning algorithm in the construction of radiobiological effect prediction models in multi-center scenarios is reasonably evaluated.

Results

The statics of test error results of the radiobiological effect prediction model established by different methods after 12 repeated experiments are shown in Table 1, and the visualization of the error distribution is shown in Figure 1. Among them, the single-center data result is the average test error of the independent model of each center; the multi-center data union result is the test error of the prediction model generated by combining the data of each center; the mean weight federation result represents the test error of the model generated by the usual federated learning method; the error ratio weight federation and fitted weight federation results represent the test error of the model generated by the soft federated learning method.

Table 1. Statics of test error results of the radiobiological effect prediction model established by different methods after 12 repeated experiments

Method	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	Mean
Single-center data	11.40	19.74	8.12	13.63	16.85	14.93	10.25	25.73	11.96	34.31	14.41	11.57	16.08
Multi-center data union	7.20	17.22	10.94	17.44	17.57	14.64	9.66	24.91	13.22	25.39	17.87	10.66	15.56
Mean weight federation	8.10	17.09	7.04	10.33	14.85	13.83	9.16	17.92	9.91	24.85	13.09	10.51	13.06
Error-ratio weight federatio													
n	7.56	16.37	6.89	9.35	14.17	13.70	9.11	16.40	9.20	20.25	12.53	10.56	12.17
Fitted weight federation	6.64	14.69	5.03	8.62	13.01	13.63	9.37	14.83	8.28	19.74	11.28	10.09	11.27

Bold indicates the best result

Figure 2. Comparison of test error distribution of radiobiological prediction models established by different methods.

As can be seen from Table 1 and Figure 2, the federated model generated by the soft federated learning algorithm using the fitted weight obtained an average minimum error of 11.27 with the lowest upper and lower limits of the error distribution, and the model generated by the soft federated learning algorithm

obtained the minimum error compared with other models in 12 single experiments. The results show that the prediction performance of the federated model generated by the soft federated learning algorithm is better than that of the federated model generated by the usual federated learning algorithm and the multi-center data union method.

Figure. 3. Visual test results of the radiobiological effect prediction models established by different methods.

The visual test results of the radiobiological effect prediction models established by different methods are shown in Figure 3, indicating that the prediction curve of the federated model constructed by the soft federated learning method can better fit the distribution of multi-center test data points.

Conclusion

Theoretical analysis shows that the soft federated learning algorithm can build a federated prediction model with better prediction performance by only sharing a small amount of data between different centers. Experimental results show that the prediction performance of the federated model generated by the soft federated learning algorithm in the construction of the radiobiological effect model in a multi-center scenario is better than that of the models generated by other commonly used methods. Theoretical analysis and experimental results show that the soft federated learning algorithm has the potential to be used to alleviate the current situation in which artificial intelligence technology is showing a trend of deglobalization in some specific fields.

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